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Identifying Areas of Vulnerability to Flood Risks using Topographic Wetness Index, Case Study Al-Shirqat City

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Abstract: *The evaluation of the effect of the flood risks is done by the taking into account of the various factors that are the topography, climate and land use. In addition, one can identify the regions that are susceptible to flood by knowing the factors and doing the necessary procedures, thus, reducing the risks that floods carry. The primary objective of this research was to find out the flood hazardous places in Al-Shirqat through the Geographic Information Systems (GIS) technology. The research was carried out by the measurement of the Topographic Wetness Index(TWI) and the thematic maps were made to show the study results in the areas susceptible to flooding in Al-Shirqat city. The study emphasized the large gap in the TWI that was split into five major levels. The areas that are really high and very high-risk areas are the ones that have a high TWI values and the areas that had floods in the previous years.*

Key words: *Flood risks; topographic wetness index; Al-Shirqat city; Al-Jirnaf valley; Umm ash Shababit valley.*

1- INTRODUCTION

Floods are among the most common types of natural disasters. They occur when water inundates normally dry land. Floods often result from heavy rainfall, rapid snowmelt, storm surges caused by a tropical cyclone, or a tsunami, among other causes[1].

The province Saladin Governorate has witnessed a wave of floods in recent years, mainly attributed to unprecedented weather fluctuations accompanied by heavy rainfall. Among the most significant floods were the Al-Jirnaf Valley flood in 2017, the Umm ash Shababit Valley flood in 2024, and the impactful Tigris River flood that affected many areas in the province of Saladin Governorate . This is illustrated in Figure (1).

Fig .(1) shows the two valleys of Umm ash Shababit and Al-Jirnaf and the floods that occurred in them

If we consider the geographic features of flood-prone areas, we notice that mountain ranges, rivers, and the steep valleys they flow through often play a significant role in triggering this natural disaster[2]. Seasonal floods or sudden flash floods, resulting from dams that intensify their impact and consequences in many cases, can cause devastating effects. The aftermath and damages of flooding can include loss of life, building collapses, and destruction of agricultural and livestock resources[3].

A study was conducted on the vulnerability of flood hazards using the topographic index in the city of Al-Shirqat, located in the Saladin Governorate. This study was prompted by a recent wave of floods that affected the city in the past few years. One of the main causes of these floods is the expansion and encroachment of population into flood-prone areas without implementing necessary flood mitigation measures. Insufficient drainage systems within urban areas, lack of preservation of natural waterways through their filling or utilization for construction and agriculture, haphazard construction along riverbanks, low-lying areas, and water flow paths, as well as various other factors such as accumulation of waste, sedimentation, growth of trees and plants in watercourses, have contributed to the occurrence of these floods.

2-MATERIAL AND METHODS

2-1 Study area location

The city of Al-Shirqat is located in northern Iraq, approximately 115 km north of Tikrit, within the Saladin Governorate. It lies between the longitudinal coordinates of ($^{\circ}00'50''42$) and ($^{\circ}00'30''43$) E, and the latitudinal coordinates of ($^{\circ}15'00''34$) and ($^{\circ}00'50''35$) N. The city covers an approximate area of 177 km². The Tigris River runs through the center of the city, and there are two main valleys, namely Al-Jirnaf and Umm ash Shababit Valleys [4], as illustrated in Figure (2).

Use digital elevation models (DEM) covering the study area from Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM-DEM) data with a spatial resolution of (10*10) meters per cell. The surface drainage network for the study area was derived using the (Arc GIS 10.3) software from the digital elevation models. These models were also used to extract flood-prone areas using the Topographic Wetness Index (TWI).

Study area location Fig .(2)

2-2 (TWI) Topographic wetness index

Before starting the extraction of the Topographic Wetness Index (TWI), the surface drainage network for the study area was derived using the (Arc GIS 10) software from the digital elevation models,

following the methods described in [5]. The total stream orders in that area were found to be five, the Al-Jirnaf and Umm ash Shababit Valleys were delineated precisely.

The topographic wetness index, also known as the compound topographic index, is a steady state wetness index. It is commonly used to quantify topographic control on hydrological processes[6][7]. This technique is used to estimate soil moisture content identify areas that are likely to be watersheds based dependence on terrain analysis. The TWI is calculated in a GIS environment using surface analysis and hydrology tools to compute the flow accumulation and slope using DEM as input. The popular formula for computing TWI as in equation (1) [8], [9]. These two attributes were computed separately in ArcGIS. Therefore, the GIS equivalent equation of TWI as in equation (2)[10],[11] .

$$TWI = \ln(\gamma / \tan(\beta)) \dots (1)$$

$$(2)..... \quad TWI = \frac{(flow-accumulation)*Pixelsize^2}{\tan(slope(rad))}$$

Equation (3) was adjusted to accommodate undefined values for flow accumulation and slope. In the case of border pixels used in ArcGIS, their flow accumulation values are set to zero. To prevent undefined output raster results, a unit magnitude is added during the computation of TWI. Similarly, slopes that reach a value of zero also lead to undefined pixels. To address this issue, it is recommended to incorporate a tangent function for nearly flat land areas, thus avoiding division by zero[12]. Taking these considerations into account, the modified TWI computation, as described in equation (3), can be expressed as follows [13]:

$$(3)..... \quad TWI = \frac{(flow-accumulation+1)*Pixelsize^2}{0.00565 + \tan(slope(rad))}$$

Where: 0.00565 is tan of a flat land close to zero slopes .

3-METHODOLOGY

The techniques utilized for computing TWI are grounded in DEM analysis, which enables the efficient identification of flood risk vulnerability. To accomplish this, a Python tool was created, leveraging the modular builder in ArcMap. The key steps of this study are depicted in (Fig. 3). The initial step involves identifying and delineating the drainage network using the DEM through the following procedure. It's worth noting that DEMs might contain depressions or sinks that can impact drainage analysis. Consequently, a "Fill" tool is employed to eliminate these sinks and ensure the uninterrupted flow of water, which is essential for accurate drainage extraction. Subsequently, the flow direction is determined by calculating the direction of flow from the filled DEM. This algorithm assigns a flow direction (typically measured in degrees) to each cell based on the steepest downhill slope. Additionally, the flow accumulation is computed to establish the number of cells contributing flow to each individual cell. Higher values of flow accumulation indicate areas with more accumulated flow, typically associated with larger streams shown in Figure (3).

Fig .(3) Description of the study area and hydrological characteristics: (A) DEM of the study area at 10 m of resolution; (B) FlowDirection Map of the Studied Area; (C) Flow Accumulation Map of the Studied Area.

The first step in stream network delineation involves establishing a threshold for flow accumulation in order to extract the primary stream network. This threshold depends on the characteristics of the area and the desired level of detail[14]. If a higher threshold is chosen, larger rivers will be included in the extracted network. Next, stream orders are assigned to the extracted stream network to indicate the

hierarchical position of each stream segment within the drainage system. The commonly used Strahler stream order is typically applied. When extracting basins from a Digital Elevation Model (DEM), the process entails identifying and delineating the areas that contribute water to specific pour points or outlets in the terrain. This process, commonly referred to as watershed or basin delineation, is crucial [15]. Once these procedures have been performed, it becomes possible to map the flood risk vulnerability by calculating the Topographic Wetness Index (TWI) [16].

Topographic Wetness Index Algorithm

The TWI algorithm is commonly discussed in hydrology-related studies [7],[17]. It is versatile in the sense that it can be applied to any Digital Elevation Model (DEM), regardless of its resolution, as the resolution of the DEM is a crucial factor in generating accurate TWI values. Understanding the potential areas of water accumulation during unexpected times can be of practical importance. Furthermore, this knowledge can also be useful in identifying areas where water resources can be accessed in times of need, as every raindrop that accumulates contributes to the replenishment of groundwater over time. Figure (4) illustrates the calculation process of TWI, starting from the initial DEM input [18].

Fig.4. Sequence of turning a DEM into calculated TWI surface

4-RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, the performance of different wetness indicators was evaluated based on their ability to accurately predict the spatial distribution of wetlands. It is essential to recognize that uniform parameterizations were used in order to achieve this. Consequently, the expected distribution of wetlands is solely influenced by the topography and not by spatially variable parameters. This is an evolving characteristic of the model simulation. The topographic wetness index (TWI) is calculated by employing an input fill sink and a flow accumulation digital elevation model (DEM) [16]. The TWI analysis is carried out following the analysis of stream networks, which involves organizing a network of streams within a specific region using flow accumulation information. The value of flow accumulation, which is analogous to a river, is utilized to explain the flow accumulation process. The branches of hydrographic network were digitized according to [19]. Their pattern is dendritic. The main catchments are illustrated Figure (5).

Fig.5. Desirable TWI classification map of Al-Shirqat city

The results of the flow accumulation analysis indicate that higher values are associated with larger areas where a substantial amount of water has accumulated, thereby impacting soil moisture levels. Conversely, higher values obtained from the slope calculation indicate the presence of steep areas that promote water flow. The Topographic Wetness Index (TWI), which is derived by combining these factors: contributing area and slope, ranges from 1.5 to 25.5.

The higher values indicate large contributing area coupled with low slope and hence a greater potential for water concentration and the lower values indicate high slopes where water is free to drain. The dark brown color in Fig. 6 has an Index value greater than (20.7) TWI index. This location has a sloping slope, which increases the possibility of large water puddles. On the other hand, The yellow color refers to a low TWI index value Between 1.5 to 6.2.

Fig.6. Levels of Flood Risk Vulnerability in the Al-Shirqat city

5- CONCLUSIONS

The utilization of (DEM) data proved valuable in the assessment of flood vulnerability in the city of Al-Shirqat. The flowchart presented in this study demonstrates an effective approach for extracting and analyzing the TWI index. By integrating the TWI index with zonal statistical analysis, it becomes possible to identify areas at risk of flooding. This data is not only instrumental in evaluating flood damage but also plays a crucial role in disaster preparedness, an essential aspect of effective disaster management.

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